

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRINCIPLES AND THEIR ACHIEVEMENT BY IMPLEMENTATION OF NOVEL AUTOMATED CONTROL SYSTEMS BASED ON RESOURCE EFFICIENCY APPROACHES

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Abstract

Economical and engineering substantiations are discussed for one particular way to implement the circular economy principles to support the Sustainable Development Goals formulated by the UN. It is discussed, how it is possible to include the circular economy principles in the development requirements for the different kinds of automated control systems. The subject matter is about the circular economy principles and one possible way for their achievement through development and implementation of the novel kinds of automated control systems. The goal is in developing of the approaches to design novel kinds of automated control systems with additional resource saving functions. The tasks are in reformulation of the circular economy principles in the form of development requirement for novel kinds of automated control systems, in development of approaches based on mathematical optimisation procedures to design the novel automated control systems providing the resource saving operation, as well as in consideration of the particular example about the electric drive to show the opportunities of novel automated control systems to provide the agreement with all circular economy principles though energy saving. The methods are based on mathematical modelling of the processes to represent of different automation objects though the systems of ordinary differential equations, on formulation and consideration of the correspondent optimisation problems with necessary additional restrictions to agree with the circular economy principles, on utilisation of numerical methods and computer simulations to represent the properties of the automation objects, as well as on application of free open source Scilab scientific-oriented software. The results are in the formulated requirements for novel automated control systems agreed with the circular economy principles through providing the resource save operation, in developed approaches to formulate and to represent of the correspondent optimisation problems, as well as in considered particular results showing the possible effects for the circular economy from implementation of novel energy saving automated control systems in electric drives. The conclusions are that circular economy principles can be achieved though implementation of the novel kinds of the automated control systems allowing to provide resource saving operation, that development of such novel resource saving automated control systems can be based only on using the complicated mathematical maintenance necessarily including of computer simulations and calculations, that novel energy saving automated control systems can allow decreasing about 50% the power supplied to accelerate electric drives, so it will be possible to save the batteries and to decrease the carbon emissions indirectly through decreasing of the recharging cycles.

Keywords: Circular Economy; Automation; Control System; Mathematical Modelling; Optimisation; Computer Simulations.

Introduction

The different novel challenges are actually the global in sense because of they cannot be resolved by the separate countries and social groups, so the Sustainable Development Goals was formulated by the United Nations for all the world independently of state borders and social stratifications. To build the circular economy is one of the critically important achievement envisaged to provide almost the all of the Sustainable Development Goals, but to build such circular economy is actually the difficult problem required politic, economic, engineering and social substantiations. The principal difficulties are in development and implementation on

novel technologies both agreed with the circular economy principle and both provided the economic effectiveness with minimum social aftermath under forming the novel labour markets due to changing of required skills and contents for vocational and higher educations. Taking into account all these circumstances, it is more reasonable to have several stages to implement the circular economy worldwide, so that to simplify the politic, economic, engineering and social substantiations for each of these separate stages and to use the having experience from the previous stages. Of course, that it is reasonable to envisage all these stages, so that the initial stage must be the simplest, but each the next stages must be more complicated.

Each of economics kinds are actually based on the correspondent technologies level, so implementation of circular economy must principally involve the correspondent technological development, and more of this, it is necessary to exclude a lot of different habitual already technologies inherent for the linear economy. All these is the really difficult problem even from the pure technical point of view, but, besides, it is necessary to have a lot of investments agreed with the effects of wished economic expedient to renovate a lot of industrial production fields as well as a lot of services and consumers industries. Of course, that development and implementation of the technologies for the circular economy actually require the long time, and it is really suitable to envisage several consistent stages to do it as was described above. Technologies are actually divided on different subject fields, and it seems reasonable to divide development and implementation of the technologies for the circular economy on the stages covering the different separate technologies fields. The automation engineering is the important technologies field having the significant development last decades and providing the noticeable improvement of the production, services and consumer industries, including to have the sustainability under the global emergencies like the COVID-19 pandemic or military conflicts activations. We can see at present, that the novel automation engineering digital technologies are suitable both for the long times existed and both for the recently developed principally new automation objects, so it seems, that it is reasonable to start technological renew for the circular economy from development and implementation exactly of the novel automated control systems. Development of the new generations of the automated control systems suitable for the circular economy requires understanding how to formulate of the novel demands on the properties for such systems and how exactly to take into account these novel formulated demands to design such systems. It is clear understood, that clear vision of the possible ways for achievements of the circular economy principles through implementation of the novel automated control systems is critically important for efforts in supporting the circular economy implementation instead of the linear economy to provide the Sustainable Development Goals formulated by the UN. Besides, adaption with the circular economy principles can be considered as the way for further development of the automated control systems, because it requires a lot of different novel and more perfect approaches and methods comparing with the existed conventional approaches. Thus, the theme of this research is actually in current interest, because of full agreement with the modern challenges in circular economy implementation regarding with the Sustainable Development Goals formulated by the UN, and it will allow to develop the more perfect automation engineering technologies.

Analysis of last achievements and publications

Nowadays, Ukraine is in a huge environmental and economic crisis. To ensure the exit from the crisis, Ukraine needs to abandon the approach of a linear economy based on the principles of "take, make, use,

waste" and go to the circular model that provides sustainable development and is based on principle "extract, produce, take, make, use, repair or recycle, reuse". In particular, circular economy promises to ensure economic prosperity within ecological limits[1].

For Ukraine, this is significant not only to get out of the crisis, but more to ensure resource efficiency, including energy, which is important for national security. Reducing the pressure on resources and the construction of a circular society should be an urgent task for Ukraine. The experience of doing European business approves that business in the European Union no longer considers the environment separately from economic development, which is provided solely through the efficiency of resource consumption and reducing pollution. It is in the context of Circular Economy Achievement Plan (CEAP) [2] as one of the key components of the European Green Deal, which is enabled the EU to achieve a fair, climate-neutral, resource-efficient and competitive economy.

The rational use of resources in industry in combination with improving environmental indicators should be a priority for Ukrainian business in the context of circularity and sustainability. And this is possible through the strategy of resource efficiency. The focus of resource efficiency should base on R-framework [3]. R-framework of CE could lay in action determined by Standard 59004: Refuse, Reduce, Repair, Refurbish, Remanufacture, Repurpose, Recycle, Recover energy, Re-mining etc [4]. Those particular R-actions ensure extension of product life cycle, reconstruction, value creation that correspond to circular economy concept.

One of the mechanisms for minimizing the negative impact of industry on the environment is the introduction of such an organizational approach in the enterprises, which achieve an increase in the efficiency of resource consumption and reduction of pollution, which can be achieved through automation.

We have a lot of researches about improvement of the automated control systems through implementations of different additional functions for them to provide the more quality operation in various sense. Thus, in the research [5] the automated control programs for the industrial supply systems are considered to enable the energetic optimization during exploitation, and it is discussed how future building automation systems should be designed for this purpose, taking into account that standard programming does not allow to use some complex algorithms. The research [6] deals with the automation and control systems improving the energy performance of buildings to reduce their energy consumption and emissions regarding with the European Union conducted policymaking within the area of combating climate change, so that we can see in this research the example of the policymaking effect on the engineering solutions through pushing of energy saving automation systems implementations. In the research [7] we can see optimisation of the parameters for the intelligent PID controller position control of a nonlinear electro-hydraulic system with uncertain valve characteristics and supply pressure variations to have the better results than the classical PID controller in tracking the test signals under various supply pressures and

valve modes. We can see from this research [7], that improvement of automation systems can provide more effectiveness for different fields, because of the considered electro-hydraulic systems have an important role in different applications like vehicles, robotic manipulators, excavator and boring machines and others. The research [8] is about certain control and automation engineering problems concerning safety of the technological operations for the horizontal transportation of nuclear fuel within the enterprises' sites, and the principal attention was directed to minimizing the transportation loads on nuclear fuel by means of decreasing the accelerations under the motion on the unmanned wheeled transportation platform. This research [8] is actually important to reduce the impact of hazardous nuclear materials on personnel through implementation of the unmanned vehicles for horizontal transportation operations of the nuclear fuel assemblies. It is necessary to note, that automation engineering involves not only the pure technical problems, but also a lot of important multidisciplinary problems covering the fields of interaction with the humans for example. Thus, in the research [9] we can see the dynamic automation system improved through providing of the adaptively allocated functions between humans and machines during the exploitation. Besides, we can refer to the research [10] focused on the acceptance and the intention to use the automated shuttles among the human through example of the representative sample of French citizens. This research [10] and the similar researches are actually important for automation engineering to provide the more suitable ways for implementation of novel automation systems. In generalizing concluding from the noted above we can mark, that improvement through implementations of different additional functions to provide the more quality operation is one of the important ways for development of the automation systems at present.

Highlight of the earlier unresolved parts of the general problem. Aim of the study

It is clearly understood, that implementation of the circular economy must be supported not only by the policies, the economics and the opportunities of zeroing different emissions in the environment, but also by the correspondent technological development of the production and consumer industries. Such technological development is the really complicated problem, because of a lot of existed different habitual already technologies suitable and inherent for the linear economy must be fully excluded from usage. So, the principal problem is actually in agreement of technological development with the circular economy requirements, but to consider this problem it is strictly necessary also to take into account existed opportunities of pure engineering solutions. At the same time, we can see that the most of the existing researches about the circular economy not take into account the pure engineering solutions in the direct view, so they have the limited opportunities to consider the problems about the technological development required to support the circular economy transition. From other side, we can see a lot of researches about the automation engineering di-

rected to development of the automation systems improved through implementations of different particular additional energy saving functions required for providing the circular economy principles. Although, we have a lot of results about the energy saving automation control systems, but all these results have the particular nature, so we have actually no the conventional generalised approaches to design the novel kinds of the automated control systems improved through implementations of different additional functions to support the technological development for circular economy transition. Taking into account all noted about circumstances, the purpose of this research is in development of the ways for achievement of the circular economy principles through implementation of novel automation control systems with the additional different resource saving functions. Realisation of this formulated purpose requires the multidisciplinary approach involving both the circular economy and both the automation engineering.

To realize the purpose this research it is planned to solve the follows tasks:

- establishment of correspondence between the circular economy principles and the additional resource saving functions for the novel kinds of the automated control systems;
- development of the generalised approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions;
- making the necessary computer simulations for particular illustration of the developed generalised approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions.

To solve the noted tasks, it will be used the circular economy concept in coupling with the theory of optimal control based on the final representing of the mathematical models in the form of the first ordered ordinary differential equations system with the initial and final conditions as well as the stability conditions under the small disturbances. The computer simulations will be accomplished by using the corresponded numerical methods and the Scilab free open-source software.

Materials and methods

A lot of researches consider the circular economy from the point of view only recycling materials to provide of their usages repeating [11, 12]. At the same time, this point of view is very limited, because of it is really difficult to resolve the global challenges like zero pollution or zero carbon emissions achievements only by recycling of the materials. Circular economy concept is more complex and does not limited only recycling. Despite the fact that recycling materials providing of their usages repeating is really important for the circular economy, it must be in coupling with other ways allowing to provide of minimum resources utilisation. Besides, we have a lot of types of materials with significantly limited opportunities for recycling, and the carbon emissions produced by the power supply industry are the examples of its. In this way, minimizing of production amounts to avoid the wastes is significant

required for the industries creating the resources with limited possibilities of recycling, but such minimizing is actually the minimizing of supply from the economics point of view, and it will have unpredictable influences on the social and economic processes, if it will not be in agreement with the demand especially in the case of the energy supplying due to sensitivities of consumers to the prices on the power. In fact, decreasing of the energy supply under the fixed demand will predictably lead to increasing of energy prices on markets in a short-term perspective. Obviously, energy consumers will try to reduce their energy consumption to decrease the demand on the markets, and they have two principal ways. First way is in decreasing of the business activity and the own production, but this way can lead to destroying of the business and the enterprises. Second way is in implementation of the energy efficiency technologies providing the same business activities and the same production amounts of the enterprises with the low energy consumption to compensate the high prices on the energy, if it will be possible. It should be noted, that realisation of the second way can save the business and the enterprises under the high prices on the energy, but realisation of this way requires some time and funding to implement the novel energy efficiency technologies instead of the currently used technologies. Besides, even if having the time and the funding, it is necessary to have also the suitable production technologies providing the energy efficiency, because of developing such technologies is actually based on the existed engineering level and cannot be realised automatically through the funding only.

We can see, that rapid renovation of the enterprises through implementation of the energy efficiency technologies under the already happened increasing of the energy prices is the very difficult, and it requires the significant costs leading to impair of the enterprises on

the markets. From other side, implementation of the energy efficiency technologies can be permanent even without increasing of the energy prices, but it will not give the economic effects in the case of low energy prices creating the situation than the funding on energy efficiency will more than the price of the saved energy. At the same time, the enterprises implementing the energy efficiency technologies permanently will more sustainable under the unpredicted energy prices jumps similar to the observed [13] in 2022 in European Union (fig. 1) on the background of the unpredicted aftermath of the military conflict in Ukraine. Indeed, we can see (fig. 1) that the electricity price has the permanent changing all-time, so that from 2011 to 2021 years we had these changes are in some relatively thin interval, but in 2022 year we had the significant jump even three times for some European countries, including in Greece. Under these circumstances, permanent renovation of the enterprises though energy efficient technologies implementation independently of the current energy prices can be imagined as the way for providing the sustainability of these enterprises under the unpredictable electricity price explosion. Besides, permanent implementation of the energy efficient technologies will lead to decreasing of the energy consumption, which is equivalent of energy demand decreasing in the economics terms, so that we will have the economical mechanisms pushing to decreasing the energy production without the price explosions leading to the negative social and economic aftermath. Thus, decreasing of the energy consumption must be the principal for the circular economy striving to decrease of the consumption, because of the most of wastes created during energy production, including the CO₂ emissions, are difficult to recycle.

Fig. 1. Electricity prices in the Europe for non-household medium consumers

Although, a lot of discussed above (fig. 1) was about the energy efficiency, but it is possible considering efficiency for utilization of other kinds resources, like the water for example, so we can actually talk about the resource efficiency of technologies generally. Of course, that to provide the resource efficiency it is necessary to design the technologies by using the strictly corresponded approaches, and it is necessary to have such approaches to do it. It is actually difficult to propose the approaches to design the resource efficiency technologies in general, because of each subject field involves a lot of particularities, whose cannot be covered by the single abstract notions, so development of

the resource efficiency technologies is actually the complicate multidisciplinary problem. At the same time, different kinds of technologies both for industrial and both for household applications involve the automated control systems providing the operation modes with minimum people's participations, usually during long times. It is naturally, that the resource utilization during the operation is predefined though the controls signals forming by automation systems, so exactly the correspondently designed automated control systems can provide the resource efficiency operation, and they must be considered as the principal part of the resource effective technologies. Taking into account all these

circumstances, we can introduce the notion about the novel kind of the automated control systems based on the resource efficiency approach, so that they provide the resource minimum utilization during operation of automation objects. This novel kind of automated control systems based on resource efficiency approach can be implemented in different automation objects with different effectiveness, but exactly such automated systems are significantly important to achieve the circular economy principles in minimization of resource consumption to limit the wastes accumulation. Thus, we have established correspondence between the circular economy principles and the additional resource saving functions for the novel kinds of the automated control systems.

Last several decades, the automated control systems for different purposes acquired some similarities

$$\dot{q}_k = f_k(t, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m), \quad q_k(t_0) = q_{k(0)}, \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (1)$$

where t is the time; q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n are the parameters defining the state of the researched automation object, and n is the given count of these parameters; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m are the parameters defining the automation system, and m is the given count of these parameters; $f_k(\dots)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are the given functions defining the current velocity of the state parameters; t_0 is the given moment of the time assumed as the initial; $q_{k(0)}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ are the given values of the state parameters at the initial time moment $t = t_0$.

Choosing of the state parameters q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n and their count n as well as the views of the functions $f_k(\dots)$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ is defined by the sense and the particular building of the considered automation object, but the initial time t_0 and the initial values $q_{k(0)}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ represent the researched operational mode of the considered automation object. The parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m and their count m are defined by the design of the automation control system in agreement with the sense of the considered automation object. Having the given parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m , we can define the state of the considered automation object in general case through numerical solving of the initial-value problem (1):

$$x = x(t; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m), \quad (4)$$

where $x(t; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m) \equiv \varphi(t, q_1(t; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m), \dots, q_n(t; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m))$.

Although, the relation (4) is the result of the initial-value-problem (1), but it is impossible to obtain this relation (4) in analytical view directly from the initial-value problem (1) in the general case. At the same time, it is possible to have generally this relation (4) indirectly through the correspondent computations using the obtained numerical solution (2) of the initial-value problem (1) representing the mathematical model of the considered automation object. Thus, the initial-value problem (1) and the relation (3) allow us to represent the automation object in the view (4) through detailed

due to implementation of electronic devices, so it is reasonable to develop the generalised approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions. Further, it will be proposed the generalised approach based on reducing to consideration of some auxiliary minimisation problem to design the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions. It is naturally, that to provide the resource saving functions it is necessary to have the enough detailed representation of the properties of the automated control system and the automation object, and such representation can be provided in general case through the corresponded mathematical modelling of the processes by using the system of ordinary differential equations with the initial conditions:

$$q_k = q_k(t; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (2)$$

where $q_k(t; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m)$ is the numerical solution for the state parameter q_k of the initial-value problem (1) corresponded to the given parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m .

Although the solution (2) defines all the processes in the automation object, but the principal task is not in processes simulation, and it is in defining of the parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m to design the automation system with the additional resource saving functions. To design the automated control systems, it is necessary to define the required controlled parameter, which must be naturally defined at any time moment by the current state of the considered automation object (1):

$$x = \varphi(t, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n), \quad (3)$$

where $x = x(t)$ is the controlled parameter the researched automation object (1), and $\varphi(\dots)$ is the given function defining this difference.

Of course, that the sense of the value x and the view of the function $\varphi(\dots)$ can be defined only regarding with each particular problem, but it is not principal for us in this research. Here in this research, it is principal for us, that taking into account the numerical solutions (2), we will have the parameter (3) as the function of the time for the given parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m :

simulation of the correspondent processes though the numerical solutions (3), and this indirectly represented relation (4) can be used to define the parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m of the automation system both for the transient and both for steady operation modes of the considered automation object.

Consideration of the transient modes for the researched automation object represented through the relation (4) will require taking into account the conditions defining the initial and the final states:

$$x(t_0) = x_0, \quad x(t_f) = x_f, \quad (5)$$

where $x_0 \equiv \varphi(t_0, q_{1(0)}, q_{2(0)}, \dots, q_{n(0)})$; t_f is the given wished final time moment of the transient mode, but x_f is the given wished value of the controlled parameter (3) at the final of the transient mode.

The relation (5) will lead to the condition defining the set of the possible parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m of the automation system providing the transient mode (5):

$$x(t_f; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m) - x_f = 0. \quad (6)$$

The importance of the condition (6) is in defining the set of the automation system parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m in which the parameters providing the resource saving functions must be found. In this case the parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m can be imagined generally as the coefficients of the Taylor's series of the time dependent function representing the control providing the wished transient mode.

Thus, to design the control system for the automation object we must consider the equality (6) to represent the set of possible parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m . In the most cases corresponded with the engineering automation we will have the count of the automation system parameters:

$$m > 1. \quad (7)$$

Due to the inequality (7), the final condition (6) will define the infinitesimal set of the permissible parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m of the automated control system providing the current initial and wished final states of the considered transient mode. To provide the additional resource saving function for the automated control system we must propose the correspondent values of the control system parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m from the permissible set defined by the final state condition (6). To propose the parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m providing the resource saving functions for the automated control system we must consider the amount of the used resource by the automation object during the considered operation time:

$$F = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} f(t, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n, x) dt, \quad (8)$$

where F is the amount of the used resource; $f(t, q_1, q_2, \dots, q_n, x)$ is the velocity of resource using for the considered automation object.

The relations (2) and (4) allow us to represent the amount of the used resource (8) as the function of the control system parameters:

$$F = F(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m), \quad (9)$$

where $F(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m)$ is some function defined through the definition (13) through the mathematical model (1) of the considered automation object.

Although, it is possible to have the function (9) only in the indirect view in general, but even for this

$$J\dot{q}_1 = M(q_1, q_2), \quad M(q_1, q_2) = \begin{cases} -Bq_1 + n_D B_e q_2 - M_{df} \text{sign}(q_1), & \dot{q}_1 \neq 0, \\ \frac{1}{2} (|n_D B_e |q_2| - M_{df}| + n_D B_e |q_2| - M_{df}) \text{sign}(q_2), & \dot{q}_1 = 0, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

$$L_e \ddot{q}_2 = -n_D B_e \dot{q}_1 - R_e \dot{q}_2 + U_e(t), \quad (14)$$

case we can formulate the optimization problem in the conventional view. For the case of the transient mode this optimization problem will have the following view:

$$c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m: \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\} \in C, \quad F(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m) \rightarrow \min, \quad (10)$$

where $\{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\}$ is some set of the control system parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m ; C is the set of the permissible controls.

The set C of the permissible controls is actually defined through the equality (6), so that we will have the following definition:

$$C: \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m\} \in C \Leftrightarrow x(t_f; c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m) - x_f = 0 \quad (11)$$

We can find the control system parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m providing the additional resource saving function for the considered automation object by means resolving the optimization problem (10), and we can use the well-known engineering optimization methods [15] to do it. At the same time, application of the well-known engineering optimization methods [15] to consider the problem (10) will be complicated due to that the function (9) and the set C of the permissible parameters are defined implicit and indirectly, so do compute the value of the function (9) and to check the involving in the permissible set C for any given control system parameters c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m it is necessary to solve numerically the system of nonlinear ordinary differential equations with the initial conditions (1).

Study results and their discussion

To illustrate the possibilities of the developed of the generalised approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions we will consider the example about the automated electric drive, because wide using of it in different household and industrial systems, so that providing the resource saving functions for the electric drives allows agreement a lot of automation object with the circular economy principles.

We will use further the generalized schematisation of the electric drive allowing to consider it as the electromechanical system with interacting mechanical and electrical parts represented by means the following generalized coordinates:

$$q_1 = \omega(t), \quad q_2 = I(t), \quad (12)$$

where q_1 and q_2 are the used generalized coordinates of the electric drive; $\omega(t)$ is the angular velocity of the driven part; $I(t)$ is the electric current in the winding of the rotor of the driving electric motor.

To consider the transient modes of the electric drive with the generalized coordinates (12) we will take into account the significant nonlinearities due to the dry friction in the mechanical part, so we will have the following mathematical model of the electric drive:

$$q_1(t_0) = \omega_0, \quad q_2(t_0) = I_0, \quad (15)$$

where J is the generalized moment of inertia relatively the driven part; $M(q_1, q_2)$ is the generalized moment acting on the mechanical parts; B is the generalized parameter of the linear damping; n_D is the relation between the rotation velocities of the rotor of the driving electric motor and of the driven part; M_{df} is the moment of dry friction; L_e is the inductivity, R_e is the resistance of the winding of the driving electric motor; B_e is the electromechanical characteristic of the driving electric motor; $U_e(t)$ is the electric voltage supplying to the driving electric motor; t_0 is the moment of the time considering as the initial; ω_0 and I_0 are the values of the angular velocity of the driven part and the value of the electric current in the winding of the rotor of the driving electric motor at the initial moment $t = t_0$.

Let consider the acceleration of the electric drive from the state of the rest, so that the initial conditions (1) will be defined by the zero values:

$$t_0 = 0, \quad \omega_0 = 0, \quad I_0 = 0. \quad (16)$$

In this considered particular example about the automated electric drive, the generally introduced controlled parameter (3) can be defined as the angular velocity of the driven part, so, taking into account the definitions (12) of the generalized coordinates:

$$x = q_1. \quad (17)$$

Taking into account the initial conditions (16) and the definition (17) of the controlled parameter, the generally represented initial and final conditions (5) will have the following particular view:

$$x(t_0) = \omega_0, \quad x(t_f) = \omega_f, \quad (18)$$

where t_f is the given wished final time moment defining the acceleration time of the electric drive; ω_f is the given wished value of the angular velocity of the driven part.

To provide the transient mode (18) we will use the controlled supplied voltage:

$$U_e(t) = c_1 + c_2 t, \quad (19)$$

where c_1 and c_2 are the parameters of the automated control.

The supplied voltage (19) represents the particular case of the generally considered automation systems, corresponded to the value $m = 2$. Thus, the nonlinear ordinary differential equations (13), (14) with the initial conditions (15), (16) and with the supplied voltage (19) can be solved for the given values c_1 and c_2 , so taking into account the relation (18) we will have the functions:

$$q_1 = q_1(t; c_1, c_2), \quad q_2 = q_2(t; c_1, c_2), \quad x = q_1(t; c_1, c_2). \quad (20)$$

Due to the last relation (20) and the final condition from (18) we will have the definition of the set of the possible parameters c_1 and c_2 of the automation system providing the transient mode (18):

$$q_1(t_f; c_1, c_2) - \omega_f = 0. \quad (21)$$

The condition (21) is actually the particular case of the generally defined condition (6).

The condition (21) defines the infinitesimal set of the permissible parameters c_1 and c_2 of the automated control system providing the current initial and wished final states of the considered transient mode (18). To provide the additional used energy saving function for the automated control system of the considered electric drive we must propose the correspondent values of the control system parameters c_1 and c_2 from the permissible set defined by the final state condition (20). To propose the parameters c_1 and c_2 providing the used energy saving functions for the automated control system of the considered electric drive we must define the amount of the used energy of the electric drive during the transient mode (17):

$$F = \int_{t_0}^{t_f} q_2 U_e dt, \quad (22)$$

where F is the amount of the used electric energy by the electric drive during the time of the transient mode.

The used energy amount (22) is actually the particular case of the generally introduced amount of used resource (9). Due to the relations (19) we can represent the used energy amount (22) as the function:

$$F = F(c_1, c_2). \quad (23)$$

Thus, to find the parameters c_1 and c_2 providing the used energy saving functions for the automated control system of the considered electric drive we must solve the optimization problem:

$$c_1, c_2 : \{c_1, c_2\} \in C, \quad F(c_1, c_2) \rightarrow \min, \quad (24)$$

where $\{c_1, c_2\}$ is some set of the control system parameters c_1, c_2 ; C is the set of the permissible controls.

The set C of the permissible controls in the considered example about the is actually defined through the equality (6), so that we will have the following definition:

$$C : \{c_1, c_2\} \in C \Leftrightarrow q_1(t_f; c_1, c_2) - \omega_f = 0. \quad (25)$$

Thus, development of the automated control system (19) providing the energy saving function for the electric drive (12)–(16) during the transient mode (18) of acceleration from the state of the rest is reduced to considering the auxiliary optimization problem (24), (25) to find the correspondent parameters c_1 and c_2 , so that it is really possible to use the well-known engineering optimization methods [15] to do it.

The principal difficulties of consideration of the auxiliary optimization problem (24), (25) are due to the implicit indirect defined goal function (23) and the set of the permissible controls (25) based on the solutions (20) of the initial-value problem (13)–(16), (19) representing the considered electric drive for the given values c_1 and c_2 of the automated control system parameters. It is really difficult to solve the nonlinear ordinary differential equations (13), (14) with the initial conditions (15), (16), for the supplied voltage (19), so we will

use the computer model developed by means the Xcos tools of the Scilab software as it is shown on the fig. 2. Of course, that computation of the used electric energy (22) it is envisaged also in the developed computer model (fig. 2), but to do it we will use the equivalent representation of the relation (22) in the form of the ordinary differential equation with the correspondent initial condition:

$$\frac{dF}{dt} = q_2 U_e, \quad F(t_0) = 0. \quad (26)$$

The view (26) is really more suitable than the relation (22), if the numerical methods are used to solve the initial-value problem (13)–(16), (19) representing the researched electric drive.

Fig. 2. Computer model of the electric drive

To make the computer simulation we will use the developed computer model (fig. 2) and the following

$$J = 15 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^2, \quad B = 2,5 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}, \quad M_{df} = 12 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}, \quad n_D = 10, \quad L_e = 150 \text{ mH}, \quad R_e = 4,3 \Omega, \quad B_e = 0,82 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{A}^{-1}, \quad (27)$$

$$t_f = 5 \text{ s}, \quad \omega_f = 2 \text{ s}^{-1}. \quad (28)$$

Thus, the computer simulations allow us to represent the function $x(t_f; c_1, c_2) = q_1(t_f; c_1, c_2)$ used for defining the set (25) of the permissible controls as well as the function $F(c_1, c_2)$ used to define the goal function in the optimization problem (24) as it is shown on the fig. 3 and on the fig. 4 respectively. Of course, that the results on the fig. 3 and on the fig. 4 are corresponded to some given steps of the varied values c_1 and c_2 , but it is possible to represent these dependencies more precisely for the significant smaller steps of the varied values c_1 and c_2 . At the same time, decreasing the steps of the varied values c_1 and c_2 to represent the dependencies $x(t_f; c_1, c_2)$ and $F(c_1, c_2)$ more pre-

values of the parameters involved in the mathematical model (13)–(16) and in the final state from (18):

cisely will lead to the significant increasing of the calculation amount, so it will be required to design the special programs providing the fast velocity calculation to do it. Nevertheless, the results on the fig. 3 and on the fig. 4 give us the imaginations about the possibilities for representation of the properties of the automation objects by using a lot of the correspondent computer simulations in the considered particular example about the electric drive. Really, from the fig. 3 and the fig. 4 we can see that the control parameters c_1 and c_2 have the noticeable influences on the controlled parameter value and on the amount used electric power for the considered electric drive during the given time from starting of the acceleration from the state of the rest.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the controlled parameter of the electric drive from the automated control system parameters

Fig. 4. Dependence of the used electric power of the electric drive from the automated control system parameters

To define the optimal control providing the acceleration of the considered electric drive from the state of the rest to the wished final condition with the minimum used electric energy it is possible to use the possibilities of precise representation of the properties as shown on the fig. 3 and of the fig. 4, and a lot of the optimisation methods [14] are well-known to do it. At the same time, to solve the particular optimisation problem (24), (25) it is more demonstratively for this research to use the semi-analytical approach discussed in the article [15]. This approach is based on introduction of the auxiliary function [15]:

$$q_1(t_f; c_1, \gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)) - \omega_f \equiv 0, \quad (29)$$

where $\gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ is the auxiliary function.

The auxiliary function $\gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ introduced by the identity (29) allows us to represent the permissible control set (25) in the more suitable view:

$$C: \{c_1, c_2\} \in C \Leftrightarrow c_2 - \gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f) = 0. \quad (30)$$

This auxiliary function $\gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ represents actually the following mapping defined through the correspondent nonlinear equation:

$$t_f, \omega_f, c_1 \rightarrow c_2 = \gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f): q_1(t_f; c_1, c_2) - \omega_f = 0. \quad (31)$$

Although, the function $q_1(t_f; c_1, c_2)$ is known only in implicitly indirect view through first relation (20), it is really possible to define the separate value $c_2 = \gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ of this function for their given arguments by using the numerical methods to solve the nonlinear equation from the relation (31), but it will be required to solve the initial-value problem (13)–(16), (19) to do it. Some of the functions $\gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ for the considered electric drive are built numerically by using the interval halving method, and they are presented on the fig. 5. It is really interesting result (fig. 5), that the functions $\gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ introduced through the relation (29) are very closed to the linear function of the parameter c_1 for the given values t_f and x_f defining the final

condition from (18), although the mathematical model (13)–(15) of the electric drive is based on the nonlinear differential equations. Such linear functions $\gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)$ can be substantiated by linearisation possibilities for the nonlinear differential equation (13) for some cases and by the particularities due to the used numerical data (27). In any case, due to the representation (30) of the permissible controls (fig. 5) satisfying the final condition (18) we can consider the function (23) as the function of one variable for the given values of the final time t_f and the final value x_f of the controlled parameter:

$$\bar{F}(c_1; t_f, \omega_f) = F(c_1, \gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f)). \quad (32)$$

Thus, the constraint optimisation problem (24) for the goal function (23) of two variables on the set (25) of the permissible controls is reduced to the not constraint optimisation problem for the function (32) of one variable:

$$t_f, \omega_f \rightarrow c_1 \in [c_1^{\min}, c_1^{\max}]: \bar{F}(c_1; t_f, \omega_f) \rightarrow \min, \quad (33)$$

where c_1^{\min} and c_1^{\max} are the permissible values of the supplied constant voltage limited by the characteristics of the driving electric motor.

Fig. 5. Representations of the sets of the permissible controls satisfying the wished final conditions

We will consider further the optimisation problem (33) for the following permissible values of the supplied constant voltage limited by the characteristics of the driving electric motor:

$$c_1^{\min} = 0, c_1^{\max} = 24 \text{ V}. \quad (34)$$

The results of specially built calculations of the functions (32) involving a lot of computer simulations by using the developed model (fig. 2) for the data (27), (34) are presented on the fig. 6. The obtained results (fig. 6) show us that the solution of the optimisation problem (33) for the interval with the boundary values (34) is the following:

$$c_1 = 0, c_2 = \gamma(c_1; t_f, \omega_f). \quad (35)$$

The results (35) are in the full agreement with the article [15], and it seems naturally that excluding of the

stepwise controls due to the value $c_1 = 0$ will lead to lower consumption of the electric energy due to excluding the jerks of the electric drive at the initial time. We can see (fig. 6) also, that the control optimisation can provide about 50% saving of the used electric energy during the acceleration from the state of the rest to the wished angular velocity for the considered electric drive comparing with the nonoptimal controls, so that it is really incredible. At the same time, these results are theoretical and based on the computer simulations, so it is necessary to make the physical experiments to have the reliable substantiations for all these predicted opportunities to provide the energy saving function for the electric drives.

Fig. 6. Dependence of the used electric power of the electric drive on one parameter of the control system

It is obviously, that providing of the optimal energy saving controls (19), (35) will be difficult through the manual control, because the most of people-operators cannot physically provide the exactly required voltage to supply on the driving electric motor, and the long times experience is required for the people-operators to be close to the optimal controls manually. Although, it seems that it is possible to develop the auxiliary people-machine systems giving the help for the peoples-operators of the electric drives to provide manually the controls close to the optimal (19), (35), but nevertheless, implementation of the automated control systems with the energy saving functions for the electric drives is more suitable to decrease significantly the used electric energy.

Conclusion and perspectives of further development

This multidisciplinary research allows us to formulate the important conclusions about necessities in creating of the novel kinds of the automation systems with the additional resource saving functions to support the efforts in striving to circular economy implementation to provide the sustainable goals development.

The point of view on the circular economy only as recycling materials from the wastes to provide of their usages repeating is very limited, because of we have a lot of types of materials with significantly limited opportunities for recycling, and the carbon emissions produced by the energy industry are the examples of its. So, despite the fact that recycling materials providing of their usages repeating is really important for the circular economy, it must be in coupling with other ways allowing to provide of minimum resources utilisation. Thus, the circular economy concept is more complex and it is not limited only by recycling, but it supports any ways of consumption decreasing to minimize the wastes, so it is possible considering efficiency for utilization of different kinds resources, like energy or water for example, and we can actually talk about the resource efficiency of technologies generally. To develop of resource efficiency technologies, it is usually necessary to use the complicate multidisciplinary approaches.

The correspondence between the circular economy principles and the additional resource saving functions for the novel kinds of the automated control systems is established. Really, different kinds of technologies involve the automated control systems providing the operation modes with minimum people's participations, so that the resource utilization during the operation is predefined by the controls signals forming by automation systems. Thus, exactly the correspondently designed automated control systems can provide the resource efficiency operation, and such systems must be considered as the principal part of the resource effective technologies. It is reasonable to introduce the notion about the novel kind of the automated control systems based on the resource efficiency approach, so that they will provide the resource minimum utilization during operation of automation objects. This novel kind of automated control systems based on resource efficiency approach can be implemented in different automation objects with different effectiveness, but exactly such automated systems are significantly important to achieve the circular economy principles in minimization of resource consumption to limit the wastes accumulation.

The generalised approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions is developed. This approach is based on the improved mathematical modelling of the processes in the automation object by means the system of the ordinary differential equations with the initial conditions. It is proposed to define the parameters of the automated control system providing the additional resource saving function through consideration of the specially formulated auxiliary optimisation problem with the correspondent constraints. It is possible to use the well-known methods to solve this auxiliary optimisation problem, but the principal difficulties are due to necessities of numerical solving of the system of the ordinary differential equations with the initial conditions representing the mathematical model of the processes in the automation object to compute the value of the goal function and to estimate the constraints satisfaction. Significant com-

putation amounts are required to implement of the developed approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions, so it is possible to use in practice this approach only through the computers with the special corresponded software.

The particular example about automated control system with the energy saving functions for the electrical drive is considered to illustrate the developed generalised approach to define the parameters of the novel kinds of the automated control systems providing the additional resource saving functions. The considered electric drive is represented by means the mathematical model taking into account presence and interaction of the mechanical and electrical parts. The auxiliary optimisation problem with the corresponded constraint is formulated to define the parameter of the automated control system providing the minimum used electric power to accelerate the electric drive from the state of the rest to the given angular velocity during the given time duration. It is clearly shown, that even implicit indirect form of the goal function and of the constraint of the auxiliary optimisation problem allows to find the optimal control to accelerate the electric drive from the state of the rest to the given angular velocity during the given time with the minimum used electric energy, but only numerical methods can be used and a lot of calculation are required to do it.

It is shown, that that the control optimisation can provide about 50% saving of the used electric energy during the acceleration from the state of the rest to the wished angular velocity for the considered electric drive comparing with the nonoptimal controls, and it is really incredible. It is envisaged as the perspectives of this research to develop the special software providing the high velocity computations to find the optimal control more precisely. At the same time, all the results are built theoretically on the base of the computer simulations, so it is necessary to make the physical experiments to have the reliable substantiations for all these predicted opportunities to provide the energy saving function for the electric drives. Exactly such experiments are envisaged also as the perspective for the further researches.

References

1. De Angelis, R. (2021). Circular economy and paradox theory: A business model perspective. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 285, 124823.
2. A new Circular Economy Action Plan A new Circular Economy Action Plan. European Commission. Brussels, 11.3.2020.
3. Potting, J., Hekkert, M. P., Worrell, E., & Hanemaaijer, A. (2017). *Circular Economy: Measuring innovation in the product chain*.
4. ISO/DIS 59004. (2023). *Circular Economy – Terminology, Principles and Guidance for Implementation*. In.
5. Fuhrländer-Völker, D., Lindner, M., Weigold, M. (2021), "Design Method for Building Automation Control Programs to Enable the Energetic Optimization of Industrial Supply Systems", *Procedia CIRP*, Vol. 104, P. 229-234.
6. Engvang, J.A., Jradi, M. (2012), "Auditing and design evaluation of building automation and control systems based on eu.bac system audit – Danish case study", *Energy and Built Environment*, Vol. 2(1), P. 34-44.
7. Coskun, M.Y., İtik, M. (2023), Intelligent PID control of an industrial electro-hydraulic system, *ISA Transactions*, Vol. 139, P. 484-498.
8. Alyokhina, S., Nevliudov, I., Romashov, Y. (2021), "Safe Transportation of Nuclear Fuel Assemblies by Means of Wheeled Robotic Platforms", *Nuclear and Radiation Safety*, Vol. 3(91), P. 43-50.
9. Bernabei, M., Costantino, F. (2023), "Design a dynamic automation system to adaptively allocate functions between humans and machines", *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, Vol. 56(2), P. 3528-3533.
10. Bellet, T., Banet, A. (2023), "UTAUT4-AV: An extension of the UTAUT model to study intention to use automated shuttles and the societal acceptance of different types of automated vehicles", *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, Vol. 99, P. 239-261.
11. Deineko, L., Tsyplitska, O., Deineko, O. (2019). "Opportunities and barriers of the Ukrainian industry transition to the circular economy", *Environmental Economics*, Vol. 10(1), P. 79-92.
12. Shpak, N., Kuzmin, O., Melnyk, O., Ruda, M., & Sroka, W. (2020). "Implementation of a Circular Economy in Ukraine: The Context of European Integration", *Resources*, Vol. 9(8), 96.
13. Alyokhina, S., Nevliudov, I., Romashov, Y. (2022), "Computer simulations of controllability processes for robotic wheeled platforms taking into account restrictions of jerk motions", *Innovative Technologies and Scientific Solutions for Industries*, No. 1 (19), P. 65–75.
14. Ravindran, A., Ragsdell, K.M., Reklaitis, G.V. (2006), *Engineering Optimization: methods and applications*, Wiley, Hoboken, 688 p.
15. Nevliudov, I., Omarov, M., Romashov, Y., Muradova, V., Vzesnevsky, M. (2023), "One approach to find optimal controls for discrete dynamic systems with numerical methods application", *Advanced Mathematical Models & Applications*, Vol. 8(3), P. 548-564.